

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

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Table 1. Data Extraction Form

ID	Extraction Field
EF-1	Id: Study Id
EF-1	Source: The conference or journal in which the study was published
EF-3	Author(s), Year, Title, Venue
EF-4	Context/Scope: The research domain, application area, or problem setting addressed by the study.
EF-5	Privacy-preserving approach: Techniques, frameworks or concepts applied to protect privacy, such as differential privacy, anonymization, or federated learning.
EF-6	Semantic similarity method(s): Techniques, models or concepts applied to measure or leverage semantic similarity. Rarity-aware technique(s): Methods or concepts for identifying, analyzing, or addressing rare or outlier data points.
EF-7	AI model/architecture: Models used, such as <i>BERT</i> , <i>GPT</i> , or any custom agent-based models or concepts.
EF-8	Innovation: Summary of main novel contributions.